

Methodology Guide for Task 3.2

for the extensive sector-based cases

CzechGlobe

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INTRODUCTION

This methodology is based on the Methodology Guide for intensive place-based cases and is specifically adjusted to the extensive sector-based cases.

What is the main difference between intensive and extensive cases?

There are two main differences:

1. Number of the workshops (from here onwards the term **exercises will be used**). **We would like to ask you to provide us with:**

1. Exercise on Leverage points (Exercise 1 in this document)
2. Exercise on Indicators (Exercise 2 in this document)
3. Exercise on Broader impact (Exercise 3 in this document)

Important: It is not necessary to provide us with the exercise on Systems mapping (Onion diagram) which is obligatory for intensive cases. However, if you'd like to do the Systems mapping and Onion diagram, as it would make the next exercises easier for you, please feel free to do it (detailed description on how to complete systems mapping + onion diagram can be found here in [Methodology Guide for intensive cases](#))

2. The way to do these exercises: regarding the fact that (according to the project proposal) you and your respective advisory boards will meet at two online or offline workshops, we suggest that **you (= leads of extensive cases) complete the above-mentioned exercises by yourself. Once you have completed these exercises by yourself, you will present the outputs (leverage points, indicators, broader impact) to your stakeholders (advisory boards) during the workshops. Workshops will be a place to discuss and review these outputs with your stakeholders.**

EXERCISE 1: LEVERAGE POINTS

WHAT WILL BE DONE

Using a Leverage Points framework, you will create **a narrative of how change (= better biodiversity outcomes) in the system of your case study happens (the narrative of change).**

NOTE: By the time of completing this exercise, a case study dialogues for Deliverable 1.7 (NINA) will be finished. The leverage points you identified in Case study dialogues for Deliverable 1.7 can be used for this exercise.

Through the exercise, one or few interventions (the levers) will be chosen to explore where in the system (= your case study) they target. You will be then asked to consider how these interventions could lever changes through the materials, processes, design and intent of those systems and in what order.

!! Important note: in case you don't have intervention in your case study: try to brainstorm what things (action, processes) can be done in your case study to produce better biodiversity outcomes

Key questions:

1. What can be done in your cases to produce better biodiversity outcomes?
2. How does the intervention target the leverage points (materials, processes, design, intent)?

1 hour

GOAL

To create narratives of change as to how specific interventions create change, where in the system, through which leverage points may interventions create desired systems transformation.

OUTPUT

A narrative of change

TOOLS NEEDED

- **A4 papers**
- **Pens and markers**
- **a short ppt on leverage points** (can be downloaded [here](#))

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND - Leverage points framework

Systems are interconnected networks of actors and organisations, connected via flows of materials, information and power. Within a system thinking perspective, we can understand systems to have properties of *materials*, *processes*, *design* and *paradigms*. These properties are leverage points at which we can intervene to change the system towards more sustainable outcomes.

We use the following four categories that characterise leverage points: 1) *materials* 2) *processes* 3) *design* and 4) *intent*. Starting from the deepest, *intent* relates to the worldviews and paradigms that are being embodied and enacted by the system. *Design* refers to the structures, actors and organisations in the system and how they interact with each other. *Processes* refer to the feedbacks or procedures that move materials around the system, and *materials* are the flows of matters within the system, such as money or fabrics and other resources.

The Leverage Points framework says that a change can be created in a system by targeting leverage Points. Shallower leverage points are usually easier to see and create change, but they do not change the system very far initially. Deeper leverage points are harder to see, but will create more fundamental change. They do so because changing e.g. intent necessarily requires change in all the shallower leverage points.

Further reading:

Abson DJ, Fischer J, Leventon J, Newig J, Schomerus T, Vilsmaier U, von Wehrden H, Abernethy P, Ives CD, Jager NW, Lang DJ, (2017) Leverage points for sustainability transformation. *AMBIO* 46 (1):30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-016-0800-y>

Fischer J, Riechers M (2019) A leverage points perspective on sustainability. *People Nat* 1 (1):115–120. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.13>

Leventon, J., Buhr, M., Kessler, L. et al. Processes of sustainability transformation across systems scales: leveraging systemic change in the textile sector. *Sustain Sci* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01436-8> (examples of interventions targeting specific leverage points)

Examples of leverage points (from Fischer and Riechers 2019):

Material	Constants, parameters, numbers	Average fuel consumption of a car
	Size of buffer stocks, relative to flows	Amount of total standing timber in a production forest
	Structure of material stocks and flows	Run-off dynamics of nutrients from agricultural fields into adjacent water bodies
Processes	Length of delays, relative to rate of system change	Time it takes for the ozone hole to close after harmful emissions cease
	Strength of negative feedback loops	The extent to which a lake can absorb nutrients and thus remain clear
	Gain around positive feedback loops	The extent to which poverty leads to population growth, which may further exacerbate poverty
Design	Structure of information flows	Consumer knowledge about where certain products come from
	Rules of the system (incentives, constraints)	Policies governing natural resources, including among others taxes and regulations
	Power to change system structure or self-organize	Ability of farmers to organize the sustainable use of a communal pasture
Intent	Goals of the system	Organization of global institutions to support free trade versus global equity
	Paradigm underpinning the system	A 'green revolution' paradigm underpinning agricultural policies
	Power to transcend paradigms	The conscious shift from a growth-based economy growth to a steady-state economy

INSTRUCTIONS

1. Select the intervention(s) you would like to explore in depth as first. These can be interventions they are already trialling, or interventions selected from the P4B directory of methods. Select 1 most important intervention to start with, and maximum 2 other interventions. **In case there is no intervention in your case study, try to brainstorm what things (action, processes) can be done in your case study to produce better biodiversity outcomes.**

2. For the first intervention, discuss and write on an A4 paper (in big letters): i) the brief description of intervention, ii) who instigates the intervention, and iii) who participates in the intervention. Put this on the left-hand side of your table. Write notes in a way that you can easily translate to English – e.g. notes/bullet points not a long text.

3. Use another 4 pieces of A4 paper and label each piece as one of the leverage points (materials, processes, design, intent) – see example below. Complete an A4 sheet for each of the 4 leverage points, exploring **how the intervention selected would target each of the leverage points** (perhaps some leverage points are not included if you feel they aren't targeted by the intervention). **Write the name of the intervention on the bottom right** of each paper so you don't lose track.

Example:

<p>Materials:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Intervention</i></p>	<p>Processes:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Intervention</i></p>	<p>Design:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Intervention</i></p>	<p>Intent:</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Intervention</i></p>
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4. Put the identified leverage points (= A4 papers) on the table in the order in which the change take place, to describe the narrative of change – e.g. does the intervention target materials first, and then shift processes? Try to narrate the change across LPs.

5. Summarise the change on a final piece of A4 paper and put it at the right end of your leverage points. Try to briefly describe the change in this last A4 paper - to characterise the change that has occurred as a result of the intervention (as described in the LPs). What does the system look like after the intervention has been done?

6. Briefly repeat steps 2-5 for each of selected interventions. Make sure the name of the intervention is always included on the bottom right of each LP so you don't lose track.

7. Once you have completed these exercises by yourself, take the outputs of this exercise and present them to your stakeholders (advisory boards) in your workshop. Discuss and review these outputs with them. Revise outputs based on discussion with your stakeholders.

REPORTING REQUEST

Once you revise the outputs of this exercise based on the discussion with your stakeholders, please, **translate all A4 papers into English and summarise them in a document, in the order they were written.** Send a picture of them to the CzechGlobe team (louckova.b@czechglobe.cz) altogether with a **brief audio or video description of your narrative of change in English.**

NOTES:

EXERCISE 2: MONITORING AND INDICATORS

WHAT WILL BE DONE

A narrative of change from exercise 1 will be used to create a monitoring strategy and identify indicators of change.

1 hour

GOAL

To identify a list of indicators of change which will be used to measure success or impacts of interventions (actions, processes) implemented and monitor desired changes in the system after the project has run its course.

OUTPUT

A list of indicators and their characteristics (how they will be measured, their purpose, ...)

TOOLS NEEDED

- **A narrative of change** created in exercise 1
- **A4 papers**
- **Pens**
- **A short ppt on monitoring and indicators** (can be downloaded [here](#))

INSTRUCTIONS

1. Read the short ppt on monitoring and indicators provided.
2. Look at the **narratives of change** which were created in exercise 1.
3. **Write the selected change** on the top of an A4 paper and brainstorm **all the indicators of change** (quantitative or qualitative metric) that could be used to measure this change (*example of indicator: percentage increase in ethnic minority communities engaging with nature and the outdoors*).
4. **Discuss and write the purpose** of the chosen indicators and why they are needed and useful. Write notes in bullet points that you can easily translate to English.
5. **Discuss and write how data will be collected to measure the chosen indicators for the change selected** (*example: survey, interviews, focus groups*) and how frequently data would be collected (*for example quarterly, annually, bi-annually*).
6. **Try to** write potential obstacles that may have an impact on the use of the indicator (its accuracy or validity).
7. **Return to the narratives of change (Exercise 1) and choose another change.** Briefly repeat steps 3-6 for this change.
8. **Once you have completed these exercises by yourself, present the indicators you selected to your stakeholders (advisory boards) in your workshop. Discuss and review these outputs with them. Decide together with your stakeholders if each indicator meets the checklist of a good indicator** as described in the last ppt slide provided. Allow your stakeholders to make any additional inputs or changes.

REPORTING REQUEST

After the workshop with your stakeholders, please, **translate your A4 papers** into English and send them to the CzechGlobe team (louckova.b@czechlobe.cz). Lastly, please do not forget to take pictures during the workshop! ☺

NOTES:

EXERCISE 3: BARRIERS & OPPORTUNITIES FOR BROADER CHANGE

Topic for discussion:

1. What the advisory board sees as successful and failed efforts to make biodiversity a bigger priority in their sectors? Do they identify any past attempts to scale-up or scale-out biodiversity prioritisation? (*Scaling-up means e.g., to adopt biodiversity in higher policies, scaling-out means e.g., spread practices or management to other sectors/places.)
2. Looking at the proposed interventions from exercise 1, what opportunities and barriers do they identify to make broader impact?

WHAT WILL BE DONE

Identifying broader impact means that we need to look at the potential effects of interventions (see Exercise 1) that go beyond the boundaries of the initial systems where we expect change to take place. Suggest what opportunities and barriers you see in respect to potential broader changes that arise from the interventions in your systems map.

1 hour

GOAL

To think about ways to increase the impact of proposed interventions that were implemented through specific leverage points (i.e. the system properties, see results of Exercise 1) in the identified systems in your case study.

OUTPUT

Building on exercise 1 Leverage points (the points in the systems where intervention take place), exercise 3 will generate potential broader impact of the intervention(s), barriers to and opportunities for broader impact in your sector. This will be done by writing a narrative of broader impact, opportunities and barriers on A4 papers on a flipchart, or by using large-format paper (flipchart) and post-its. The description will include what the broader impact is, how it manifests, and what the opportunities and barriers are.

TOOLS NEEDED

- **Pens or pencils**
- **Optional**
 - **Post-it notes** in multiple colours
 - **Markers** (multiple colours; at least black, blue, red and green)
 - **Flipchart**
- **A set of A4 sheets** – for a narrative per broader impact, opportunity, and barrier.
- **A short ppt on barriers and opportunities for broader impact** (can be downloaded [here](#))

INSTRUCTIONS

1. Revisit **leverage points** including the narratives of change (from exercise 1).
2. **See the example** in provided ppt slides for a better idea of this exercise.
3. **Pick the first intervention** and explore potential broader impacts and the related opportunities and barriers. Ask the following questions one by one to execute the exercise:
 - a. **How would you describe potential broader impacts** in your case? Identify all relevant impacts that may occur and write them down on e.g. A4. Write down a more detailed description on an A4 paper – a narrative
 - b. **Which other sectors or policies are** potentially affected by the intervention? Here you will tap on “neighbouring” or related sectors and policies. Identify and write them down on e.g. A4. Write down a more detailed description on an A4 paper – a narrative
 - c. **Which** factors, actors, or processes **enable broader impact**? Here you will identify **opportunities** linked to your interventions and initial sector. Identify all relevant opportunities and write them down on e.g. green post-its and place them on A4. Write down a more detailed description on an A4 paper – a narrative
 - d. **Which** factors, actors, or processes **halt broader change**? Here you will identify **barriers** linked to your interventions and initial sector. Identify all relevant barriers and write them down on e.g. pink post-its and place them on A4. Writes down a more detailed description on an A4 paper – a narrative
4. **Pick another intervention** (from exercise 1) in your case and continue the exercise in a suit described in the 3rd point. Repeat this with maximum 3 most important interventions

5. Finally, debrief and discuss results. Is there anything to add regarding the broader impacts, barriers and opportunities? If several opportunities and barriers per interventions were identified, please highlight the most prominent ones. You can ask any other question that arises from the workshop.

6. Once you have completed these exercises by yourself, present the outputs of this exercises (barriers, opportunities, etc...) to your stakeholders (advisory boards) in your workshop. Discuss and review these outputs with them. Allow your stakeholders to make any additional inputs or changes.

REPORTING REQUEST

After the workshop, **please translate post-it notes and the descriptions (A4 papers) into English and summarize them in a word document**, e.g. in the order they were written or otherwise so we are able to identify their place in the template.

Make a short video, in English, to briefly summarize the information in the template and on the A4 papers.

Send document and video to the CzechGlobe team (louckova.b@czechglobe.cz)

NOTES: